

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: MULEKA****FIRST NAME: VINCENT****PROGRAM CODE: DEPI****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 1****INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did use Zotero to insert references (remove unneeded text to indicate)

The author did use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: 00%

The author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord 365 on Windows 11)

List your 6 key concepts with page number in text (then bold these terms in your RP)(samples below):

1. Essay Writing (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 6-14)
2. Punctuation (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 15-23)
3. American vs British English (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 24-32)
4. Plagiarism (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 33-39)
5. Style Guide (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 40-57)
6. Latin Abbreviations and Expressions (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 58-64)

FUNDAMENTALS OF ESSAY WRITING

1) INTRODUCTION

I am excited to finally start my doctoral studies at Euclid University after putting it off for over 3 years. I was just scared of the unknown. I was afraid of what lay ahead, especially since it had taken me over 8 years to apply after my master's degree. All these factors were almost justified when I read my introductory package and student pack. The material was intense, throwing me off balance for a few days, and I could not focus. However, as I have read it carefully several times, I am getting a good grip on what I need. I have just realized that "I need a good grip on the basics of good writing principles as a precursor to my successful journey through my doctorate studies."

2) FUNDAMENTALS OF ESSAY WRITING

Writing is communicating, and for it to be valuable, it has to follow some sound laid-down principles. We write as a way of thinking, even though it is not the most straightforward way (Greetham 2022,17). After reading and rereading the course pack, I

will have to unlearn and relearn some things to make my studies smoother. My understanding of the various sections of the course pack is outlined below.

a) Essay Writing

As an educator with over 15 years of experience, I had a good grasp of the importance and the nuances of good essay writing. After reading through the course pack, I realized that I have a lot to unlearn and relearn. Foremost, I have been acutely reminded of the necessity of my essay being easy to read and understand by all people, irrespective of their background (Cleenewerck and Gulma, 2024). As a student of mathematics in general and applied statistics in particular, I have always assumed that my research and resulting research reports would be for those in my field. This erroneous view can easily be misleading and have adverse consequences, resulting in poor academic writing. I aim to make my reports concise and easy to read. This will help reach more readers and, therefore, be more effective. I have also learned to make adequate preparations before starting the actual essay writing. Despite that, I will struggle with this for the initial essays like this one until I am used to the grind.

Apart from the whole art of writing, referencing my work is the only other part of essay writing I am still fumbling with. It is not as if I would like to take other people's ideas without giving them credit, but more of the nitty-gritty of how to reference them. I have read and reread the guidelines, but I am still not confident that I have gotten it, at least not yet. However, I am confident that I will be fine in the long run, probably after several guided edits. I am bracing myself for this part of my learning journey.

On the other hand, I was glad to be reminded just how much good editing can make one's written work stand out (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024,11). I agree with the assertion that good edits should be made, but with time between the original writing and editing. If I have someone to read over my essays, however, I will gladly skip the wait, especially since I will often be pressed for time to submit the essays.

Lastly, I had a lot to learn from the category of rules of thumb. Key takeaways from this section included striving to attain clarity in my writing, staying on task while writing, staying away from "sweeping generalities," and aiming 'to support every claim and assertion and diligently avoid plagiarism closely.' As an educator, I understand why staying focused is key to completing tasks because I preach the same message to my students. I will have to learn to write with clarity because I like storytelling.

I am looking forward to practicing the art of avoiding generalities and Plagiarism because, from my understanding, I will get them quickly from the feedback I receive from my work.

b) Punctuation

I have mentioned that I have a lot of unlearning and relearning, and this part of the ACA-401D course packs the biggest punch. I have always had challenges interpreting the

use of various punctuation marks I encounter in the books and scientific papers I have read. The challenge was so great that I assumed that there were no patterns or rules that guided me when to use them. This does not mean that I did not recognize how they changed the meaning derived from the phrases and sentences whenever they were used. I have taken some time reviewing the different ways that essential punctuation marks are used, and I am gaining some insight. I plan to keep practicing their usage and hope to improve, especially with the use of Grammarly. I am trying to observe the 'cardinal rule' to minimize their usage while keeping the meaning (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024,15). Even as I appreciate the guidance, I dare say that I was awed by how the punctuation greatly enhanced the essay by paraphrasing the same information. I firmly believe that this will help reduce the glare of Plagiarism. I am hoping to learn the use of those punctuation marks to prepare myself for the journey ahead since I am sure there will be many papers to read and some to edit and review (Turabian et al. 2018, 17).

Despite the apparent importance of each punctuation mark, I will be using quotation marks much more because they lend themselves to unavoidable usage when writing citations and referencing (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024,23). This is more so for the many instances I will have to lift a quote as it is from the source document. While mentioning writing references and citations, I would also note that the use of appropriate brackets, commas, question marks, and full stops was of great interest to me, and I have yet to master and understand how to use them fully.

c) American vs. British English

As a Kenyan citizen, I learned the British version of English, as did all other countries that Britain colonized. As an educator, I have worked for over 12 years teaching British English. However, four years ago, I started to work with American English, and the contrast has been causing me a lot of trouble, from pronouncing words to writing them. I am going through a learning curve, having to combine both versions of English since I need my students to understand me, and I also have to keep my prior learning since my work with American students is not permanent. Indeed, both American and British English are more similar than different (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 25). This can be seen in how some words cannot be changed despite being used in different versions of English. However, this does not change the fact that it is important to consistently write in a specific version of English. This consistency helps lessen any difficulties in understanding whatever information I have to pass along. A case in point is when I am dealing with my students at the moment, and I use British spelling in a word, it creates confusion that takes a long time to correct and get back on track. I have more than enough reasons to believe that sticking to one version is very important. For example, I'll pick the use quote "I got a pen" as is used in American English to mean "I have a pen" in British English, While the exact phrase "I got a pen" in British English could give the impression that I was given a pen as a present, that is what I was given referring to some activity or event in the past and not in the present as is used in the American English.

d) Plagiarism

I want to compare Plagiarism to the highest degree of disrespect in any field. As a scientist, acknowledging the works of those who have come before you is both respectful and also offers continuity to the knowledge being shared. Turabian puts it precisely in stating that scientists need the knowledge and works of those before them, and the cycle keeps growing (Turabian et al. 2018, 19). More often, the work we quote is only gently mentioned, and this helps the reader know where to get the full details if needed. I want my work to be appreciated through proper citations and referencing. Therefore, I will hold this art of acknowledging others for their existing work, which will be making a basis for my own, very close to my heart. It is the best way of building communities of knowledge. It is important to note that with the research now primarily done on the internet and not reading physical books, the temptation to plagiarize is high (Burton 2021, 2).

Even though I already hold Plagiarism in utter disgust, the course pack has taught me a few new nuggets of wisdom about ways of properly citing and referencing, especially per the styles recommended at Euclid University. Some of the key points here include minimizing the number of direct quotations, citing the source even when I have paraphrased, and ways of writing long direct quotations (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 36). Of course, I am still struggling with citing correctly, especially from different sources, but I am sure I will get better with practice.

e) Style Guide

Initially, the guide on style was restrictive. However, I have learned that the guide helps limit the wandering and focuses me on things that matter. Once I have settled on the style, I would have a direction to follow, as opposed to if I had all styles available, then I would have mixed choices. Sticking to a particular style, like the Chicago rules (Turabian), means I will write my papers in formats that my tutors will recognize and have ready guidelines for grading that are more uniform for all my fellow students within the institution.

As part of the guide for style, I have understood that the style for punctuations and how to use them to be consistent and uniform according to Euclid rules will put me on the path to success (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 41).

Considering the Chicago style, some specifics are familiar to me, like the proper use of acronyms and the way of beginning sentences with an upper-case letter, prefixes, and adjectives for geographical terms. At the same time, there are parts that I have not understood just yet. These include the use of quotations, how to best use compound words, and what to avoid. I am still working on comprehending the page formats. Once I have comprehended them, my writing will go way smoother. Professor Cleenewerck did an excellent job in helping me understand the connection between style and choice of English (Cleenewerck 2016)

f) Latin Abbreviations and Expressions

With many languages in the world, some ancient like Latin and some modern and emerging, there is always the need to share commonalities and to understand the terms that different languages lend to be used in other languages. I understand that Latin is one of those languages that has been around the block, and some original works in key research fields were in this language. The process of sharing knowledge means some terms are not translatable. The list has a lot of apparently standard Latin abbreviations that I have not met before, although I am glad there are a few I already knew, like A.M., P.M., etc., and vs. (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 60). That leaves a lot of abbreviations I have seen in passing, never seen or could not associate with Latin, but most importantly, did not think of what they could mean in English

3) CONCLUSION

As my very first academic work to kick off my doctorate in biostatistics, I want to learn enough basics of writing to be ready for the scientific writing ahead of me. I did not do much writing papers during my previous studies because the level of study considered the field as mathematical. Hence, rigorous work was to solve mathematical and statistical problems and questions rather than write scientific reports and papers. My studies at Euclid will be different, with a lot of scientific reports and papers. The ACA-401D course pack and the accompanying short video have set me off on the right path, and my writing skills will improve as I travel through the periods in the course.

I look forward to the feedback so I can use it to improve my future work.

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